

MIDDLESEX UNIVERSITY

The Theory of Nine (9) Points

The Evolutionary Stages of the Adolescent Users' of Illegal
Psychotropic Substances Behaviour and their Parental Environment.

Observations from Clinical Case Studies.

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CONTENTS	PAGE
SUMMARY	3
CHAPTER ONE – INTRODUCTION	4
CHAPTER TWO – SCOPE AND AIMS OF THE RESEARCH	6
2.1 General	6
2.2 Background	7
2.3 Bibliographical Review	8
CHAPTER THREE – RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	10
3.1 General	10
3.2 Method Description	10
3.3 Method Evaluation	14
CHAPTER FOUR – RESEARCH ACTIVITY	15
4.1 About the Application Framework	15
4.2 About the Active Users	16
4.3 About the Semiotic Analyses	18
4.4 About the Parents and the Broader Social Environment	18
CHAPTER FIVE – RESEARCH RESULTS	20
5.1 About the Profile of the Medium User	20
5.2 About the Formation of a Personal Therapeutic Request	21
5.3 About the Theory of Nine (9) Points	21
5.4 About the Parental and Broader Social Environment	27
CHAPTER SIX – CONCLUSIONS & PROPOSALS	29
NOTES & BIBLIOGRAPHY	32
APPENDICES	40
Appendix A Questionnaire: Research and Background of the Psychotropic Substances Use	
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	46

SUMMARY

Aims of the Research

The explanation and description of the Theory of Nine (9) Points, which is concerned with the behavioural stages of the users of psychotropic substances, before and during their involvement with the use. The description of the medium user's profile. The description of the process for the formation of a personal therapeutic request for the users. The evaluation of the influence the parental and broader social environment exercises upon the users.

Research Methodology

It concerns the case study and desk research. It involved two random and representative samples: Thirty-eight (38) active users and twenty-one (21) users' parents and members of the broader social environment. It also involved a research through my personal sessions records and a research through the relevant bibliography (articles, books, Internet).

Method Description

It involves the design of a questionnaire concerning the research on the background of the psychotropic substances use, which was submitted to the users. It also involves the conduction of interviews with users and their parental and broader social environment. Finally it involves the semiotic analyses on the questionnaires' results, the interviews and the notes on previous sessions with users and their parents from my personal records.

Conclusions and Proposals

As far as the future user is concerned, we can observe an important emotional imbalance and inactivity for long periods before his entrance into substance use. There are serious communication difficulties within the family and the broader social environment. After his entrance into substance use, the user develops a behavioural code with particular emotional answers. He/she uses substances as "regulators" of his feelings. During the process of addiction recovery, the formation of a personal therapeutic request manages the causes of entrance into the use, as well as the grief caused by the final break from the use. We can also observe a raise in the use of psychotropic substances, especially those with repressive effects on the central nervous system. The age limit, which concerns the entrance of the new user, is decreasing.

The study suggests the development of the Theory of Nine (9) Points. The formation of a relevant questionnaire using the Theory of Nine (9) Points, which will concern the users, as well as their parental and broader social environment. It also suggests the analysis of the emotional behaviour of the users in order to understand their emotional intelligence. Finally, it suggests the systematic study on the first two points of the theory, so that they will be applied in the prevention programmes.

Chapter One

INTRODUCTION

What leads to drug use and what leads away from it when you are already involved?
What is the meaning of the user's behaviour?
Why does he seem so distant and strange?
Why isn't he like everybody else?
What are you going to do concerning his parents' panic and anger?
What is the extent of their responsibility?
What is the extent of the user's responsibility?
Which is your position?
What is they all ask of you?
Why so much pain? Why can't they all be saved?
How can you be certain that you are heading towards the right direction when everything around you seems to collapse?
What is that finally leads to addiction recovery?

It is true that one of the most important issues raised during the formation of a personal therapeutic request for a user of psychotropic substances (as far as the evaluation of his motives is concerned), is the difficulty the specialist faces in defining this path in relation with a reliable instrumental framework of reference (Matsa K. 2000²¹). The above core questions are of the kind which need an immediate answer every time the problem of dependence appears, and are characteristic of the confusion the specialist faces, and of the hard psychological and social position of the dependant himself as well as of his environment. Consequently, the first contact with the user is expected to rather make the picture more blare than make the situation more clear (Matsa K. 1998¹⁹). In fact, one has the impression that things are hard, very hard, almost impassable. Each effort seems to be in vain, whether it is for the users who are entering under their "own will" or for those who enter in haste, under the pressure of their own people (Alektoridis P. 2003²).

On the other hand, if one listens to the narration of several user cases one will begin to observe particular facts which seem to resemble the cases of other users, as far as the path of use and the way these people feel is concerned (Matsa K. 2001²²). I definitely do not mean that all cases are the same or that the specialist should follow a non-flexible form of therapeutic practice (Koutouvidis N. et al 1998¹⁴). What I observe is a certain sequence of facts during the course of a user's life. What is interesting is that these facts seem to be independent of the kind of psychotropic substances that are used and abused. Furthermore, we can also observe a relevant course of facts in the users' environments, and especially their parental environment (Aggelou M. 2001¹).

The above observations are very important, because it seems we could suppose there is a sequence of general behavioural stages in the development of the path of psychotropic substances use (Bergeret J. 1999³; Bouras et al 2000⁵). This

supposition could apply order in chaos, in the stream of use and in its seeming “out of line” course. If these facts are organized properly, we could construct a framework of reference, a “driver’s map”, which with relevant certainty could inform us about the user’s path and about our corresponding therapeutic choices. Of course, I do not consider this “cartography” to be the most important element of the therapeutic process, but it is at least supportive and encouraging to be familiar with it. I personally consider such a process as of vital importance and mainly as a precondition for every specialist who is involved with the use, the users and their environments in any manner.

The above thoughts lead me to the fulfillment of the present research, taking also into account the limited bibliography on that issue (at least to the extent that my research on secondary literature has revealed), especially in Greece (Koutouvidis N. et al 1998¹⁴).

Chapter Two

Scope and Aims of the Research

2.1 General

The scope of the present research is to describe the form of organization of the facts that seem to be common in the course of the psychotropic substances users' life, as these are revealed during their clinical observation, and to suggest a reliable and instrumental framework of reference. The presentation of facts is primary, as these are reported on the field, and it involves the least possible interpretative and typological references. Thus, the present research could constitute an essential guide for further analysis, for relevant comparative research or for further development of the theory.

Therefore, the aims of the research are:

1. to describe analytically the behavioural stages the users seem to follow before and during their involvement with substances,
2. to describe a useful profile of the medium substance user, pointing out their general characteristics, during the time they are involved with the substance use,
3. to describe the suggested process for the formation of a personal therapeutic request for the user and,
4. to evaluate the role of the parents and of the broader environment, with reference to the ways in which they are involved with the substance use problem.

The first aim refers to the essence of the present research: The analytical description of the behavioural stages of the users during their course of use, as these were reported from the interviews, the questionnaires and the sessions in my private office, but also from my experience as person in charge at the prevention department in the *Kentro PsychoKoinonikis Ypostirixis* (Centre of PsychoSocial Support) of the Amarousion Municipality. This report leads to the second aim, which is the description of a model of the medium user, based on the general characteristics that appear in the behavioural stages. Being aware of these general characteristics and taking into consideration the special needs and motives of the particular user (i.e. his particular characteristics), we can exercise therapeutic interventions for him/her, aiming at the formation of his/her own request to proceed with the restructuring of his/her behaviour towards substances, which is also the aim of the process for the formation of a personal therapeutic request. The fourth aim is rather supportive of the third, in the sense that it is important to be familiar with the behavioural and emotional fluctuations of the user's parents and broader environment. This is because during the first months of the approach the user's psychological condition is rather changeable and we should create balance within his/her environment through our correctional interventions.

2.2 Background

From 1995, and especially from 1997, until 2000 I was actively involved with the field of substance prevention (primary) at a community level, as person in charge at the prevention department of the *Kentro PsychoKoinonikis Ypostirixis* in the Amarousion Municipality (Papanikolaou Ch. 1994³²). The prevention programme includes particular activities, which lead to the averting of the involvement of new users. Before that I carried out a research within the municipality, which's aim was the recording of the problem and the description of the attitudes, views and level of awareness by the various social groups (Papanikolaou Ch. et al 1995³³). The need for their sensitivity, as well as for the facilitation of their communication, was obvious. The philosophy of the *Total Political Prevention* (Papanikolaou Ch. et al 1994³¹; OSAP³⁰) was considered as the appropriate approach for the application of a prevention programme. The above approach concerns a programme, which's aim is the creation and preservation of a network of agents and legal persons that would act as a fabric of timely social intervention. What impressed me, especially during the sessions with the parents, was their intensively negative feelings towards the use and the users. I refer to people who did not face a problem of substance use within their environment. Thus, they sometimes felt furious towards the drug dealers, other times they were angry with the strong-headed users, other times they felt fear and sometimes a strange indifference towards the issue. Their emotional blocking was obvious. I consider that many times this is the biggest problem in the issue of substance use. This is what keeps the people who are not involved with the use from realizing and understanding the nature of the use. At the same time, what is indicative, from the experience that comes from the systematic occupation with treatment (second degree prevention) and social integration of users (third degree prevention), in my private office, from 1995 until today, is that there is a serious difficulty the user faces in the formation of his/her personal therapeutic request. That is, a difficulty on the part of the user to identify the real circumstances under which he/she lives, to understand by experience the real role substances play for him and decide to change all that. To personally ask for help. This is a time consuming, painful process, which involves strong reactions, outbreaks, acting outs and relapses. My experience has also showed how important the support from his/her environment is (i.e. by the parents, relatives, partner and friends). *Co-dependence is a generalized situation with strong feelings of anger, anxiety and fear, which we observe within the user's environment.* The above issue constitutes the most important problem concerning the management of crisis.

All of the above issues have their beginning and end in the understanding of the user's personality, as well as of his environment.

2.3 Bibliographical Review

A research has been undertaken through the research studies, scientific articles, studies, seminar notes. Also, I carried out a research through the Internet, using key-words, such as: personality characteristics, substance use and theories on personality in substance use, based on the Greek and International bibliography. Finally, I completed a general bibliographical review, through which I made the following observations (see NOTES & BIBLIOGRAPHY):

- a) in the Greek bibliography (whether it concerned studies made within the country or translations of other studies) the issues of concern are:
- the kinds and pharmaceutical texture of psychotropic substances,
 - the various medical issues (hepatitis, HIV virus)
 - the substitutes (methadone)
 - the correlations between legal and illegal psychotropic substances
 - legislation and the work of justice
 - criminality which is related with the use
 - the broader provision of information to the public, especially on issues which concern prevention
 - the various programmes against drugs
 - the broader social causes of use
 - the involvement of politics in the issue of use

A lesser concern is observed on:

- the users' families
- the work and activities of therapeutic communities
- research on social groups (mainly young people)
- the psychological and social factors concerning the use

- b) in the International bibliography the general concern is on:
- issues on the provision of information to the public concerning prevention
 - counseling services on the issues of the HIV virus
 - the substitutes (methadone, but mainly new types)
 - general medical and pharmaceutical problems caused by the use
 - theories on biology and genetics which concern the use
 - issues of legislation
 - issues of deviation and criminality
 - issues on legalization
 - issues on de-penalization
 - especially issues which concern the legal psychotropic substances (mainly alcohol, nicotine, volatile)
 - issues on the *peer cluster theory*
 - issues of personal development and social skills
 - the relationship between social dynamics and the use
 - behaviours of addiction

Conclusively, we can argue that the reports on the user's personality are general, do not provide a precise picture, while they do not cover the need of understanding the nature of the user's personality as a whole (Marselos M. 1997¹⁷). Thus, those reports are either disperse within other subjects that concern the use or refer to typologies of the kind of personality disturbances (borderline, psychopathic, antisocial) (Zlatanos D. et al 2001⁸; Michalareas E. 2003²⁷). Also, it is really difficult to locate a clear description of the behavioural stages of the user, which relate to the period before and during the use. However, we should mention the multi-factorial dimension of the phenomenon of substance use and the substantial difficulty in the formulation of theories and practices with immediate results. The contemporary view on the multi-factor dimension refers to the tri-polar nature of the causes of each toxic substances addiction: 1) the toxic product and its influence on the organism, 2) the personality of the toxic substances addict and all the emotional elements which constitute it and 3) the influences of the various environments this personality was in from the infant age and afterwards (Aggelou M. 2001¹; Michalareas E. 2003²⁷; Bergeret J. 1999³).

Chapter Three

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 General

The research involved the combination of **desk research** and **case studies**. It was quantitative, as far as the questionnaires are concerned, and qualitative, as far as the semiotic analyses and the structured interviews are concerned.

The collection of data was conducted as follows:

- For the 1st aim (the analysis of the behavioural stages) I provided questionnaires and conducted structured interviews with active users.
- For the 2nd aim (instrumental profile of the medium user) I completed a semiotic analysis of the questionnaires, the structured interviews with the users and the notes on previous cases of users kept in my personal records of sessions.
- For the 3rd aim (process for the formation of a personal therapeutic request) I carried out a semiotic analysis of previous cases of users from my personal records of sessions.
- For the 4th aim (evaluation of the parental and broader environment of the users) I conducted structured interviews with persons from the environment of the active users.

The choice of sample (users, parents, broader environment) was random, and was based on my current record of patients. The participants had full knowledge of the research scope and participated by their own will. All issues of ethics (secrecy, anonymity) have been secured.

3.2 Method Description

The process of the collection of data was as follows:

1st AIM (Analysis of Behavioural Stages)

I provided a total of thirty-eight (38) especially formulated questionnaires to thirty-eight (38) active users of psychotropic substances. Furthermore, within the same sample I conducted thirty-four (34) conducted interviews.

The Sample

The sample (n=38) had the following characteristics:

- The users' ages were from 16 to 24 years. Mean age: 20 years.
- 32 Male, 6 Female
- All participants were in constant contact with psychotropic substances at least eight (8) months before their participation in the research
- The main substances used were: Heroin 65%, Heroin and Hemp 25%, Hemp 10%

- During the research they made use of the main substance at least once within the past 10 days.
- During the research they were in constant weekly contact with me, beginning at least a month before.
- There was a commitment for their abstinence from every psychotropic substance at least 12 hours before their examination through the questionnaire, as well as before the interview.

The Questionnaire

(Appendix A includes a copy of the Questionnaire)

Research and Background of the Use of Psychotropic Substances

General

The aim of the present questionnaire is a primary estimation of the causes, which lead the respondent to the use of psychotropic substances. It also examines the circumstances under which the use takes place, the consequences of the use, and makes a primary estimation of the current psychological and social situation of the user.

Directions

The questionnaire is provided through personal contact and covers 1-2 sessions (each session lasts 45 minutes). It is not given during the first sessions, but only when the interviewer considers that there have been developed feelings of security and trust on the part of the respondent. Before the beginning of the interview, which is made through the reading of the questions, the respondent is assured that his/her answers are secret and the results will be used anonymously in the present research.

Analysis

The questionnaire is estimative and informative, and it is divided into seven categories. More precisely:

- 1) Questions 1,5,6 and 7 estimate the present circumstances of the use and reveal the main substance in which the respondent is addicted to. This information is important because the planning of the de-toxification and, also, the primary planning of the process of addiction recovery will be made according to the main substance.
- 2) Questions 2,3 and 4 evaluate the user's stand towards legal psychotropic substances. In this way, we can have a total picture of the user towards addiction.
- 3) Questions 8,9 and 10 provide information concerning the user's introduction to the use. They also provide a primary description of the feelings caused by the use. This is very important, because it allows the evaluation of the kind of defensive mechanisms and the difficulties raised during the phase of de-toxification.

- 4) Questions 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16 and 17 make an estimation of the user's current social and financial situation and especially the kind of relationship he/she has with his/her family environment. The above elements are very important and are related to the kind of support the user will be provided with during the phase of de-toxification and the phase of addiction recovery.
- 5) Questions 18, 19, 20 and 21 provide information on a possible medical and psychiatric record, which is related to the use or not. This information will be evaluated and used whenever necessary.
- 6) Questions 22, 23, 24 and 25 provide information on the legal consequences of the use, but mainly give the picture and the degree of the user's growing anti-social behaviour. Also, they provide information on whether the user would like to use our sessions for his/her defense in the court.
- 7) Questions 26, 27, 28, 29 and 30 evaluate the user's personal therapeutic request. They relate to whether the user considers himself/herself ready to finally – and not temporarily – cut-off the use. They are considered to be the most important questions, and the answers to them will be evaluated together with the user's total picture.

Concerning the issue of the control questions, we should take into consideration that their treatment is difficult, and that we should generally avoid in any case any disturbance in the user's fragile trust towards the specialist. We should also take into consideration the fact that the user's personality is manipulative and his/her feelings change easily. Nevertheless, I indicatively mention questions 7 and 29, which could be considered as control questions and cannot both be answered with "YES". Also, the present questionnaire does not include questions, which concern the degree of bodily and psychological dependence, neither questions, which concern phenomena of tolerance and addiction, because they would make the questionnaire very complicated. However, we consider as given the fact that the request for help by a specialist reveals a degree of tolerance and addiction that the user cannot manage.

Apart from the suggested types of questions, I also used three mixed types (i.e. category & information, category & multiple choice list, category & open-ended answer). The reason for the above is that the three additional types of questions provide me with access to more research material.

More specifically, the types and numbers of questions are:

Type of Question	Number of Question
Information	1
Category	7, 12, 14, 15, 16, 22, 26
(Category & Information)	2, 3, 4, 11, 19, 20, 21, 23, 24, 25
Multiple Choice List	5, 8, 9, 10, 28
(Category & Multiple Choice List)	13, 27
Table	6
Evaluation	17 (Likert scale)
Open ended	18, 30
(Category & Open ended)	29

Note: The evaluation of questions 29 and 30 will lead to Classification.

The Structured Interviews

The term “structured interview” is used to describe the open form of verbal communication, which seeks to confirm or reject previously studied suppositions through the introduction of a logical series of questions. Thus, after the provision of the questionnaire and within a short period of time, a session was scheduled, during which the interview with the users took place. The interviews had two aims: to clarify a few vague points raised by the answers in the questionnaires, and, mainly, to fulfill an in depth study and estimation of the users’ feelings, needs and desires, during the use, as well as during previous periods of their lives. In certain cases, the interviews took more than one session because the material under study was big enough. Concerning this type of study, at first there was a thought of using psychological tests, such as the MMPI personality test or the TAT test of psychoanalytic origin. However, these tests were rejected, because they were not designed to fulfill such in depth studies, and therefore would limit the material under study.

The results of the questionnaires and the interviews were carefully evaluated and compared, so that I could have a complete picture. The common key-words found or implied in the questionnaires and the interviews were evaluated through the semiotic technique. The results from this procedure were the elaboration of the gradual behavioural stages before and during the use, and the formation of the model of the medium user based on the cases examined.

2nd AIM (Instrumental Profile of the Medium User)

The elements of the model of the medium user raised from the study were compared with previous data, included in my personal notes from the records of patients and sessions. This research involved data collected until three years ago and it concerned twenty (20) cases. Their choice was random (through the number of record and a choice of the first twenty [20] numbers from a table), and they were divided in two categories: the first ten (10) cases had a positive development and the last ten (10) cases did not continue. The choice was limited within the three-year time period, because clinical observations have shown that there are major changes within greater time periods. The final result was the suggested instrumental profile of the medium user I have worked with during the last years.

3rd AIM (Formation of a Personal Therapeutic Request)

Besides the fact that the above research, through twenty (20) cases from my personal records during the last three years, has contributed to the formation of the medium user’s profile, it has also provided me with enough data for the formation of a personal therapeutic request in the use of psychotropic substances, through the semiotic technique mentioned above.

4th AIM (Evaluation of the Users' Parental and Broader Environment)

After the completion of the questionnaires and interviews with thirty-eight (38) active users, there was an effort to conduct structured interviews with their parents (76) and the most possible persons from their broader environment (relatives, friends, partners). The sample was formulated as follows:

- Out of the total seventy-six (76) parents, seven (7) were dead.
- Twelve (12) were separated or divorced.
- Twenty-two (22) of them were excluded by the users themselves.
- Seventeen (17) did not want to participate.

The final number of people who took part in the 4th aim were twenty-one (n=21): fifteen (15) mothers, three (3) fathers, two (2) brothers and sisters and one (1) partner.

3.3 Method Evaluation

The scope of the present research is the formation of parameters and the composition of the elements of the four research aims, without focusing on the partial but on the total. Great attention, of course, is given on the main aim, which is the presentation of the behavioural stages of the user of psychotropic substances. The two research samples (38 active users and 21 persons from the users' parental and broader environment) are random and, based on my experience, representative. The total of research tools (questionnaire, structured interviews, semiotic analyses) and their combination allow the requested in depth study. Also, the further examination through my personal records of notes and sessions, render the results safe and valid. I believe that a greater number from both samples would raise the validity of the results.

Chapter Four

RESEARCH ACTIVITY

4.1 About the Application Framework

Since the present research is based on work (Work Based Studies), I consider necessary for its fuller understanding to present the framework of work in which it was developed.

Since 1995 and until today I keep a private office as counselor for mental health, with specialization on the users of psychotropic substances and on their family and broader social environment.

Generally, the counselor for mental health applies in his practice the principles of counseling: *Counseling is a process of interaction between the counselor and the persons who attend to him, which approaches relationship, emotional, cultural and socioeconomic issues aiming at the development of their potential.* It is a confidential process, it concerns single persons, couples or groups of people and its main characteristic is the particular conversation, which comes from the dynamics of the formulated counselive relationship. Through this conversation, a more rational approach to the personal problems and the definition of the problems are obtained, so that their fuller understanding will lead to the discovery of solutions. We can apply counseling to manage and solve particular problems, to take decisions, to manage issues of self-development, to manage crises, to improve relationships, develop self-knowledge and to manage feelings of internal struggle. For the accomplishment of the above aims, different bibliographically indicated methods of counseling are used. Also, the practice of counseling is applied within a deontological framework and with the support of surveillance. The general aim of counseling is the improvement of the quality of life of the persons who are counseled through the improvement of their psychological health and balance.

I have made an extensive reference concerning my work as a counselor for mental health in the field of toxic-addiction in Part 2.2 *Background* (Chapter 2 *scope and Aims*) (KE.TH.E.A 2000¹¹). What is important to clarify here is the fact that the research participants are persons from my current list of patients. The precondition for their participation was that they would continue with their counseling for their detoxification and the formation of their personal therapeutic request for their addiction recovery, after the completion of the research. The above was of main importance, because the feeling of continuity after the research was beneficial for the research itself, since the kind of relationship formed between us allowed for a more direct communication, which drastically diminished the psychological pressure caused by our exposure in any kind of tests.

4.2 About the active users

The circumstances under which my work with the users took place were indeed hard (Alektoridis P. 2003²; Pouloupoulos Ch. 2001³⁶). That is because when the user is still involved with the use, he/she develops a particular type of behaviour: he/she is strongly manipulative and chaotic (Matsa K. 2001²²). In fact, the user is anti-social and seeks for the benefit he/she will acquire from the circumstances around him/her. Also, his feelings are changeable. The user likes provoking and does not like to co-operate. All of the above of course, have got their explanations, if one takes into consideration the circumstances in the street, the kind of relationships the user develops and also the pharmaceutical dynamics of the substances. My primary intention was a sample of forty-five (45) active users. However, five (5) of them did not want to co-operate by any means, not only by presenting their objections, but with strong reactions against any reference on my behalf. Another two (2) were excluded by me, since I observed certain characteristics in their behaviour, which would render their participation in the research invalid (disturbances in their short-term memory, delirious ideas), and since their general picture “did not inspire trust”. Thus, the final sample was formed with the participation of thirty-eight (38) persons.

My co-operation with the above sample was generally good, during the provision of questionnaires as well as during the process of the structured interviews. What I observed was that what made most of them to participate and co-operate with me was not a supposition that “I would take more notice of their case and therefore help them be cured”, but a rather narcissist view that “a specialist pays attention to me and is occupied with me because I am interesting”. I should also note that, especially during the interviews, the climate was different between boys and girls (Matsa K. 2001²³). The boys answered in a more direct way, without having particular questions, while the girls showed interest and involvement through questions.

The process of the questionnaires’ distribution was normal and the questions have been positively accepted by all participants. Concerning question 9 (reasons for the introduction into the use) there were many who mentioned that they have not thought about it a lot before, while many were impressed by question 7 (re-definition of the desire for use). Some of them reacted with negative comments to question 20 (treatment in psychiatric hospital) and to question 25 (imprisonment). All questions were answered by all participants. Out of the total of the participants, two (2) of them called for postponement of the session and a new session was arranged. The rest came to the sessions as scheduled. All of them kept the commitment for recession from psychotropic substances at least 12 hours before the process of the questionnaire provision.

The process of the interview conduction was interesting and complicated. The session, which involved the interview, was a week after the session, which involved the completion of the questionnaire. Out of the thirty-eight (38) participants, and while their session was scheduled, four (4) of them (three [3] boys and one [1] girl) did not call to inform me that they would not come. At first, they did not answer my calls, or were absent. Later, they stated that they did not wish to co-operate. They also said that for the time being they would not continue their contact with me. They did not mention any reasons that related to the research. In all this process I avoided

coming in contact with parents or other people from their environment for deontological reasons. Concerning these cases, I did not replace them and I did not remove the questionnaires. Also, nine (9) boys cancelled the session at the last moment. Their excuses had to do with their “bad mood today”, or “something came out”, “I don’t want to come today”, “I think that finally I don’t want to give this interview!”. In these cases, I preferred not to schedule another session for the interview through the phone, but to discuss the issue with them through a session. During that session, most of them mentioned that they “wouldn’t go well with the interview” and that was because they were perhaps “not ready for in depth confiding”. My effort concerned their encouragement and support. First of all, the aim was to diminish their anxiety. I reminded them that their participation was voluntary, and that if they did not want to proceed, their wish would be respected. However, I pointed out that it was important that they would continue with their effort, and that in this way they would manage to “break a wall” and prove themselves that they can turn the things inside them that make them scared and/or insecure. I also mentioned that I would be by their side through all this effort. After that we arranged a new session for the interviews. Out of the nine (9), seven (7) of them proceeded as scheduled. Two (2) of them did not keep their commitment for recession from substances. I did not arrange a new session for them, I mentioned how sorry I am about the way they face reality, and waited for their call at their wish. After a few days they called me, asked for forgiveness about their behaviour, and a new session was arranged where they proceeded normally and the interviews took place under regular circumstances.

Almost all interviews begun as a sequence of the questionnaire. I gave particular emphasis to questions 8 (introduction to the use), 9 (reasons for trying the first few times) and 10 (reasons for continuing with the use). Questions 16 and 17 (parental environment) were of enough concern. Questions 26, 27, 28, 29 and 30 (about the recession from the use) were very interesting to the users, and, to my surprise, were extensively answered.

Other questions concerned:

- the feelings caused by the use during the first trials and now
- why do they believe they feel this way during the use? (so differently and yet so much the same, as one user mentioned)
- How do they believe the others perceive them?
- Which were their life conditions before the use?
- In which way did they communicate with their environment before the use and in which way now?
- How do they feel about other users?
- What is their difference from the other users and from those who are “clean”?
- How do they perceive their own selves as users?
- What do they think about their future?
- What would they really like to be different around them?
- What can they do about the changes they wish to come?

I believe that questionnaire, as well as the interviews, provided enough data on the issues, which concern the circumstances before the use, during the period of introduction and during the course of use.

About the semiotic analyses

The semiotic analysis is the technique, which conceptually compares the content of texts, isolating points, or key words and/or phrases. The key words and phrases in the present research concerned the users' personality characteristics, the users' behaviours, the relationship between the users and their parents, peer to peer groups, issues of diagnosis and therapeutic techniques about the users and their families.

In the present research, the semiotic analysis was on:

- The notes from the interviews with the users and the questionnaires results, for the formulation of the behavioural stages.
- The notes from the interviews with the users' parents and broader environment, for the estimation and analysis of the nature of their participation in the formation of these stages.
- The notes from previous cases from my personal records of sessions, for the formation of a method for a personal therapeutic request for the user.
- The already mentioned review on the selected bibliography, for the validation of the present research findings.

4.4 About the parents and the broader environment

There were two characteristic facts, which lead to the final formulation of the sample (n-21) among the users' parents and broader environment: The exclusion of twenty-two (22) parents by the users themselves and the refusal by seventeen (17) parents to participate in the research. These facts are characteristic of the way the family framework is usually formulated, after the introduction to the substance use at home: refusal for communication at the part of the user, cancellation and rejection on the part of the parents. In fact, the feelings that prevail interchangeably on both sides are anger and fear. Similar circumstances and almost the same emotional fluctuations are observed within their social environment.

At first, the number of users who demanded that their parents would not participate was greater, a fact which is expected under the formatted climate. Some of the users, who's embarrassment towards the argument was obvious, were convinced by the argument that "it is important for the users themselves to have their parents participate, in the sense there is a serious possibility that through their parents' participation they might re-define their stand towards the users". There were also users who wanted their parents to be excluded so that they "would be protected" from a consuming and stressful process (as they consider would happen). However, what I realized was that some of them were trying to avoid "their parents realizing at length the meaning of the fact that they are users". They were also convinced through similar arguments. However, they were users who had great anger and did not change their minds by any circumstances. Characteristic is the fact that the greater their parents' insistence was to participate the more the users were unyielding.

The stand of the parents who refused to participate was also interesting. Of course, most parents were interested in the nature of the research and mainly asked

for reassurances that their and their children's participation was for the common good. When they were convinced, through conversation, there was no problem in their approval and agreement for the under age users' as well as for their own participation. The parents who did not want to participate had a different frame of thought: they insisted that they "were only interested in their children" and that they "did not want to be occupied with other problems and thoughts". What was obvious from the conversations I had with the parents who finally refused to participate, is that they were generally not willing to co-operate, not even the least. They perhaps could not admit that they had a share of the responsibility for their children's present condition. I also have to note that the users who did not give the interview are related to the group of parents who did not want to co-operate. Nevertheless, at least as far as it came to my knowledge, no parent had officially forbid his/her child's participation to the research.

This whole situation rather reminded me of the especially negative stand towards the users, that I faced, as responsible for the prevention department of the Center for PsychoSocial Support, during my contact with parents who had no problem of substance use within their families (Part 2.2, Background). The fury against the dealers, the anger against the users, fear and indifference, are all characteristics of their emotional blocking. Most of the times, this is the greatest problem concerning the use. I consider that the problem I faced with the parents who refused to co-operate was similar.

Thus, the final sample (n=21) of the parents and the people from the broader environment constituted of fifteen (15) mothers, three (3) fathers, two (2) brothers and sisters and one (1) partner. The ratio between mothers and fathers in the sample was random, but I think it is representative. The brothers and sisters and the partner accepted to participate at once and our co-operation was very good. This fact is probably due to their relative distance from the problem, without that meaning that they do not have an active presence.

The aims of the interviews and the relative questions concerned:

- the description of the picture the users present to them,
- the estimation of their feelings towards the users,
- the estimation of the way they react towards the users,
- the confirmation of the degree of their desire and potential to change the way they react.

Each interview took a session with each of the interviewees.

Chapter Five

RESEARCH RESULTS

5.1 About the Profile of the Medium User

The active model of the medium user, as that was formed through the results of the questionnaire and the personal structured interviews with the active users who took part in the research, as well as the data from my personal records of sessions, is the following:

- The medium age is twenty years (20),
- Seven (7) out of ten (10) are male,
- Eight (8) out of ten (10) belong to the middle socioeconomic class,
- Nine (9) out of ten (10) live with their parents or in place controlled by their parents,
- The main substances of abuse are repressive of the central nervous system,
- The medium time period of systematic use before the first session is six (6) to nine (9) months,
- The subjective degree of bodily addiction is above medium,
- The subjective degree of psychological addiction is substantive,
- Nine (9) out of ten (10) are systematic tobacco users,
- Five (5) out of ten (10) are systematic alcohol users,
- Four (4) out of ten (10) students in high-school have cut off from school for more than one academic year,
- Seven (7) out of ten (10) students in high-school have deficient attendance at school,
- Seven (7) out of ten (10) students do not systematically attend their Schools for more than one academic year,
- Seven (7) out of ten (10) have been prosecuted by police or judicial authorities,
- There was no case of HIV virus (AIDS) infection,
- Three (3) out of ten (10) were infected with hepatitis,
- Three (3) out of ten (10) make a simultaneous use of pills through legal medical recipes,
- Two (2) out of ten (10) have been having a permanent job for more than one year,
- Two (2) out of ten (10) have relationships with “clean” friends,
- Three (3) out of ten (10) have being having a permanent partner for more than eight months,
- Six (6) out of ten (10) have attended or keep attending, during the first session, a dryly therapeutic programme for a time period of one (1) week to three (3) months,
- Their medium number of relapses is six (6) before the first session,
- Eight (8) out of ten (10) entered under their parents’ or broader environment’s pressure.

5.2 About the Formation of a Personal Therapeutic Request

During the first session, the requests the users usually make are:

- To be helped to “cut-off” by themselves,
- To “convince” their parents – environment that they have no problem,
- To not continue attending (if they do) at the therapeutic community,
- To talk “freely” with a specialist.

It is easy for someone to realize the difficulty in the formation of a personal therapeutic request (Matsa K. 1998¹⁹; Paraskevopoulos N.³⁵). The relative experience, however, shows that there is no user, even the most miserable or “maniac” with the substances, that does not have a deeper need to a complete recession from the use. I should also note, that the international bibliography mentions no case of a forced psychological addiction recovery which was successful (Papanikolaou Ch. et al 1994³¹; Paraskevopoulos N.³⁵). Thus, in each case, the aim that has to be accomplished and being recognized through experience by the user is that “I have a problem with substances and I have to deal with it”. This process is indeed painful and time-consuming. Nevertheless, I consider that there are two key-factors in every successful formation of a personal therapeutic request for the user: The recognition of the facts which formed the circumstances that lead to the use and the recognition and management of the grief caused by the final recession from the substances.

5.3 About the Theory of Nine (9) Points

During the research, as well as in the past, the basic question and the essence of my thoughts concerning the users was the nature of their feelings (Zlatanov D. et al 2001⁸; Matsa K. 1997¹⁸; Bergeret J. 1999³; Koutouvidis N. et al 1998¹⁴). I consider the way they feel about themselves and about the things and other people around them to be a real problem, which is related to the use of psychotropic substances. What was made clear, especially through the interviews, and once again verified the knowledge I have from experience, is that in reality the user uses the substances – to the degree that this can be done within the frame of his addiction - as voluntary regulators of his/her feelings (Kostoulas G. 2002¹⁵). That means, that he/she tries to artificially change the way he/she feels, many times according with the stimuli he/she receives from his/her environment, not being able to bear his/her sensitivity and fight the things that hurt him/her. The empiric rule at this point mentions that the repressives of the central nervous system are used in reality to repress the anxiety or the stress, while the stimulants are used to diminish the feelings of depression. This is a secondary benefit, for which “he pays, sometimes very hard”: Rejection, mockery, and sometimes even with the user’s life.

The analysis of the user’s behavioural stages (Aim 1) lead to the formation and formulation of the theory of nine (9) points (Papanikolaou Ch. 2001³⁴). This theory analyses behaviour, having as a main guide the emotional fluctuations of the user, in five stages:

Stage 1. Before the beginning of the use.

Stage 2. During the beginning of the use.

Stage 3. During the use.

Stage 4. The vicious circle of addiction

Stage 5. At the exit from the use.

Concerning the first four stages (before the beginning of the use, during the beginning of the use, during the use, the vicious circle of addiction) the theory was based on the results from the questionnaires and the interviews with the users, the relative information from the interviews with the parents and my notes from my personal records of sessions.

The theory of nine (9) points suggests and analyses the following behavioural stages to the users of psychotropic substances:

Before the beginning of the use (Stage 1)

It is true that the period before the use has been evaluated in a single-sided manner and presents a restricted knowledge concerning the real psychological and emotional falls a young person is possible to develop, and which might be the cause of person's being vulnerable (Kefalas P. 1997¹²; Matsa K. 2003²⁴; Bergeret J. 1999³). It is this vulnerability that creates the circumstances, which make him/her more exposed, and "if found at the wrong place at the wrong time" might lead him/her to the entrance to the use (Matsa K. 2000²¹). It concerns these people who have no involvement with the use yet, but are called *potential* users (Bergeret J. 1999³).

This period is actually very important because it concerns all our activities, which relate with prevention (Bergeret J. 1999³). A prevention, however, which will not only be based on the information policies of the community, neither will be exhausted in fear, ignorance, terror, praying or exorcisms (Liappas G. 1991¹⁶; Matsa K. 2001²²). Prevention should first of all concern these persons who are vulnerable and their course of life has created sensitivities and at the same time emotional exclusions. Therefore, in order to have a real prevention against substances, we should direct our efforts towards the development of healthily scaled family and social relationships for the child and the adolescent.

That is the message that one can receive from his contact with people (users, parents, environment) who lived and experienced the problem of the use.

Before the beginning of the use, we can observe the following sequence of circumstances:

Point 1. PERIOD OF EMOTIONAL INSTABILITY

It concerns a long time period of emotional instability, which probably begins at the end of childhood and at the beginning of pre-adolescence. The present research locates the beginning of this period between the ages of 10 and 11 years. Under normal circumstances, this period includes the development of social skills, which aim at the inclusion and adjustment. The characteristic of the emotional instability of these people is their difficulty in communication. That means that they do not

express themselves and that they distance themselves from various situations. This difficulty in communication is rather permanent and lasts for a long time. In fact, what seems to be the case is that they have a difficulty in understanding their emotional situation. They have feelings but they cannot “read” and interpret them at a personal level (Aggelou M. 2001¹). This time period of emotional instability lasts for several years, without, however, causing serious concern on the part of the environment since it is not especially provocative (Matsa K. 2003²⁴).

Point 2. PERIOD OF EMOTIONAL INACTIVITY

The period of emotional inactivity concerns the adolescence period and it is usually short. It seems to come in sequence with the previous period. The communication difficulties continue to exist, however, their cost is more intensely obvious. The failures at the inter-personal level are more strongly experienced (Aggelou M. 2001¹). Often, we can observe behaviours of resignation, melancholy, or outbursts of violence in various forms. The disappointment within is great (Matsa K. 2001²²). There is often an effort for the inclusion into various activities, such as participating in politics, counter-politics or athletics, without this, however, assisting into a substantial emotional de-blocking. During the phases of isolation, the person has intense illusions of a heroic character (Bergeret J. 1999³). The main characteristic of this period is the continuous, intense and usually of a short duration changes of mood. The person’s environment reacts rather in panic or aggressively to the situation, a fact which sharpens the reactions and makes the communication gap even greater.

During the beginning of the use (Stage 2):

Point 3. INTRODUCTION STAGE

The introduction stage is the period of acquaintance with the substances and their environment. The first contact with the substances are characterized by the users as a “situation of rest and carelessness”. It is impressive that many users do not remember any details from this stage. It certain, however, that experimentation and casual use gradually acquire a primary role in their lives. We should also take into consideration the total “background” of the stage of introduction. That means that the primary role is not on the substances, as most people think, but the environment, the street, its people, and mainly, the relationships created (Liappas G. 1991¹⁶; Matsa K. 2001²²; Michalareas E. 2003²⁷). Another interesting element is the relatively reduced resistance on the part of the new user against the process of introduction, a state which is further reduced while the availability of the substance and the environment that sustains it are increased (Liappas G. 1991¹⁶). The continuously increasing occupation with the substances will end in the user’s choice on the main substance at use. This gradual occupation will soon create a dynamic relationship between the user and the effects he/she experiences through the substances (Matsa K. 2001²²). This dynamics is exclusively based on the fact that through the substances the user is

able to “orient” his/her feelings. Referring to this stage, the users characteristically mention that their “acquaintance” with the substances was their touch with the “lost paradise”. The passage to the use is the answer to the previous periods and marks the end of any internal search (Matsa K. 2001²²).

During the course of use (Stage 3):

Point 4. STAGE OF USE ESTABLISHMENT

Almost all users refer to this stage as their “honeymoon” with the substances. This is certainly not by accident. The casual use has now turned into continuous use. In other words, the user seeks for the quantities he/she needs. Emotionally he/she finds himself/herself between the satisfaction of having hold of the substances and the impatience he/she feels when he/she meets obstacles in their acquisition. As the users themselves mention, the contact with the substances is almost erotic and is accompanied by pleasure and euphoria (Marselos M. 1997¹⁷). At this stage we can observe an intense use which leads to abuse. Also, having hold of the substances, the user experiments through various ways (music, use and alcohol, sex, etc) which will increase his/her euphoric experience. This is a period of his/her integration with the important object (substances) and his/her pleasure tends to be total (Kostoulas G. 2002¹⁵; Matsa K. 2001²²; Michalareas H. 2001²⁶). Some users refer to the feeling as “swallowing the substances”. At this stage the user’s demand to continue with the use is strong. This is the reason why every serious effort on the part of his/her environment to intervene so that he/she recess from the use fails. During this period we have the beginning of the establishment of his/her psychological dependence on the substances. The period can last from three (3) to eight (8) months since the beginning of the use. However, the length of the period is differentiated according to the kind of substance.

The vicious circle of the use (Stage 4):

Point 5. STAGE OF THE USE PRESERVATION

The entrance into the stage of the use preservation is the end of almost all pleasure the user experiences from the use of substances. In fact, he/she will never again be able to experience again the feelings caused by the use at Point 4, and this is not because of the substance used but because of a certain psychological and perhaps neuro-biological condition at which he/she found himself/herself. Experiencing Point 5, many users try to change the doses or substances, or to add substances, so that they will return to Point 4. This, however, is impossible any more. This is the hard reality concerning narcotics and the first substantial shock caused by the use. As the users themselves mention, they feels as though the “substances emptied them”. Many of them think of cutting off the use (not completely though), so that the situation might change. The result would be the same. The picture of the user’s emotion is tragic: on

the one hand there is a cancellation of the recess because the decrease in the pleasure level is substantial, and on the other, the inability to cut off hurts him/her. I consider the fact of total recess from the first time the user experiences the emotions in Point 5 to be rare, because his/her desire to re-experience the whole pleasure from the use is still strong. The user will obviously pass through this many times, until he/she manages to stop or totally cut off from the use.

Point 6. STAGE OF THE USE RE-NEGOTIATION (temporary recess)

The intensity from the previous stage will create strong emotions of anger and a feeling of capability. Psychologically he/she “makes a free jump”. The user tries over and over again to feel again what he previously felt through the use, but in vain. After that he/she makes efforts to consider the facts in a rational manner, to discuss the issue with others, and most of the times he/she will be lead to recess, which is of course temporary. Apart from a few cases where the user passes to Point 6 for the first time, it has been clinically observed that the temporary recess lasts for a long time, and in some cases for many months. Thus, it is important that the specialist will recognize whether the recess is temporary or final. Also, it is important to know that besides everything else, the temporary recesses offer a chance for the user to manage issues which concern his/her environment or health problems, since he/she has entered a temporary de-toxification.

Point 7. STAGE OF RE-ENTRANCE INTO THE USE

After the temporary recess, and since the desire for use is still in latent form, the user comes back to the circle of use. The user’s aim does not change: he/she wishes to re-experience the pleasure that comes form the use and for this reason he/she will make serious efforts towards this direction. However, whatever happens, he/she will partially experience the pleasure. In this way the user will keep returning to Point 5 over and over again. The alteration among Points 5, 6 and 7 constitutes the vicious circle of dependence. There is no time limit for this stage. If the user does not die of abuse and if he/she does not finally manage to enter Point 8, the vicious circle will go on, even if the user enters a hospital or prison. That is the second shock caused by the use.

During the exit from the use (Stage 5):

Point 8. STAGE OF RE-NEGOTIATION OF THE USE (Formation of a Personal Therapeutic Request – Final recess)

What can really happen so that the user will “break” the vicious circle of dependence? The transformation of Point 6 to Point 8 is the most vital and important stage of the course of the use. And that can only happen through the formation of a personal therapeutic request. As we will see, the start for the course towards this

direction happens when the user realizes, and begins to accept the personal grief from the realization of the final recess from the substances. That is the third shock caused by the use. Many times the user feels embarrassed and depressed. The final de-toxification from the substances and the process of addiction recovery start at this stage. The development of this stage might last for more than twelve (12) months.

Point 9. PHASE OF EXIT FROM THE USE
(Continuity of Therapeutic Interventions)

At this stage we can observe the development and completion of the processes of accepting the grief and of the final recess from the world of substances. It is the period of the user's psychotherapy. Characteristic is the fact that many users describe this phase as "waking from lethargy". In reality, this is a very difficult period for both the user and his/her environment. It is very important to note that the user might be deceived and relapse. Special attention is needed at this point, because with each relapse the user might return to Point 7 and then directly to Point 5. From that point it is easy for him/her to enter into the circle of dependence, since he/she is still psychologically vulnerable. During this period, which might last for even eight (8) months, we have the completion of the user's addiction recovery. I have to note here that the results from the addiction recovery can be better and more final when the user enters a proper group programme of a dryly therapeutic community (Paraskevopoulos N.³⁵; Koutouvidis N. et al 1998¹⁴). The reason is that the user needs to be placed within the limits and framework of a group. For this reason, and even in cases of relapse or escape from the programme, the user must meet the proper support so that he/she will be able to return and complete his/her addiction recovery.

The phase of exit from the use later becomes a course out of the use, which I think never finally ends. This is because the person who was a user, has installed experiences in his memory, even of these experiences are now emotionally faded. The fact that these experiences exist is still due. That is the fourth shock from the use. For this reason, I think that through all his/her life, the ex-user should continuously focus his/her attention on the prevention from relapse by the substances and his/her course of life must be centrifugal of the circle of any kind of dependence, while this is still possible to happen.

5.4 About the Parental and Broader Social Environment

It is true that, after his/her entrance into the world of substances, the user distances himself/herself from his/her environment and his/her social environment continuously shrinks (Kostoulas G. 2002¹⁵). This results to the gradual decrease of social stimuli and pictures the user receives. The decreased stimuli result to the decreased understanding of his living conditions, and of course, the relative differentiation concerning his/her emotional reaction to them.

In general terms, the environment the user refers to is:

- Parents
- Relatives
- Friends
- Partner or Lover
- The street

The combination of the parental and relatives environment constitutes the typical Greek family environment. Characteristic is the fact that user who is at Point 4 considers symbolically as his/her “family” the street, while when he/she moves from Point 5 to Point 8 he/she makes an approach towards his/her real family environment from the start.

The families who participated at the present research had the following characteristics:

- Eight (8) out of ten (10) were middle-class
- Eight (8) out of ten (10) belonged to the middle middle-class
- Both parents have a job
- Concerning the educational level, five (5) out of ten (10) have at least graduated from High-School
- There is usually another child in the family
- Six (6) out of ten (10) families have been informed or attend a family programme at a dryly therapeutic community

The requests the parents usually have during the first session are:

- To be informed about the substances
- To talk about the problems they face as a couple after the entrance of the use at home
- If their child attended at a therapeutic community and has stopped, to “be convinced” to go on with the programme
- If they had visited another specialist, or participate in a therapeutic programme, to have “a second opinion” concerning their child’s problem.

The semiotic analysis of the results from the interviews with the users’ parents and the broader social environment, as well as of the notes from my personal records of sessions, showed that during the use: The parents face serious communication problems with their child (Demitriou A. 2002⁶). The conflicts and arguments are strong and continuous. They rarely face the problem at its real dimension (Bergeret J. 1999³). At the past, most of them had full ignorance of issues, which concerned substances, and consequently were completed unprepared when the problem came out. The fathers had a strongly opposing or passive stand against any

provisions of support, especially when the problem concerned their son (Matsaka I. 1997²⁵; Bergeret 1999³). They generally feel strong anger, fear, embarrassment, guilt and sometimes indifference. In most cases, they have ignorance of how their child feels or thinks. Sometimes their demands are exaggerating, without taking into consideration the real facts.

Concerning the psychological support by the persons (especially brothers and sisters, relatives, friends) of the broader environment, the picture is certainly more improved. What are considered to be problematic are the emotional relationships of the user during the period of the use, and that is because the partner is not prepared for such a kind of cohabitation. Most of the times, these relationships are broken after the procedure of the user's addiction recovery. The emotional relationships between users are pathological by definition.

Chapter 6

CONCLUSIONS – PROPOSALS

The primary aim of the present research was, through the evaluation of clinical cases, to present the basic points in the course of life of a medium user of psychotropic substances, before and during the use. The research concluded with the formulation of the theory of nine (9) points, which constitutes a model of a framework of reference for this course. The process included the co-estimation and evaluation of the user's parental and broader social environment. Furthermore, the research includes the proposal of the points, which are directed towards the assistance of the formation of a personal therapeutic request of the user.

The conclusions concerning the profile of the medium user, as this comes out of the present research, are the following: It seems that the age limit of the entrance of new users, who experience a contact with psychotropic substances, tends to decrease (Aggelou M. 2001¹; Kalarrytis G. 2001⁹; KETHEA 1999¹⁰; Matsa K. 2000²¹; Matsa K. 2003²⁴; Michalareas E. 2003²⁷; OKANA 2000²⁹). That means that younger people are involved within the circle of use, and, because of their age, their psychological defense is decreased. We observe the strong phenomenon of multi-use (Aggelou M. 2001¹; Kalarrytis G. 2001⁹, KETHEA 1999¹⁰; Kokkevi A. et al 1994¹³; Liappas G. 1991¹⁶; Matsa K. 2003²⁴; Michalareas E. 2003²⁷), especially during the stage of the establishment of the use (Point 4), but also during the stage of the preservation of the use (Point 5) and the stage of the use re-negotiation – temporary recess (Point 6). The users are addicted very soon, and therefore become psychologically dependent very soon (OKANA 2000²⁹). In Greece, the users mostly prefer the substances, which are repressive of the central nervous system (Aggelou M. 2001¹; Kokkevi A. et al 1994¹³; Papanikolaou Ch. et al 1994³¹). That seems to be due to the need for a decrease in the strong psychological pressure they feel. Often, the use is combined with alcohol and a permanent medical description, while the use of tobacco is considered as given (Demetriou A. 2003⁷; Moros N. 1998²⁸; Kokkevi A. et al 1994¹³). The use of alcohol is also intense during a time period after the addiction recovery. Their involvement within the circle of use also creates serious disturbances within the other fields of their lives (Michalareas E. 2001²⁶). Thus, there are problems at school, or with keeping their jobs, their relationships or their friends. The deviant behaviour is for many cases given, and it includes their involvement with the police and judicial authorities. Many times they present medical problems, and in some cases we can observe the development of serious psychopathology (Liappas G. 1991¹⁶). Asking for help takes a long time, and most of the times it is done under the pressure of asking for “returns”.

Conclusively, we can consider the user as a person with serious difficulties in communication, vulnerable enough, sensitive, with decreased psychological resistance and with decreased quality of life (Marselos M. 1997¹⁷; Matsa K. 1997¹⁸). The formation of a personal therapeutic request for the user is the necessary precondition for the beginning of their addiction recovery (Liappas G. 1991¹⁶; Matsa K. 1998¹⁹). During the course of this formation, the first step is the exposure of the past and the search for all the reasons, which lead to the use. These reasons are mentioned in the two periods before the beginning of the use (Points 1 and 2). This

seems to be necessary, because the facts of the past must be studied in their real dimension, be “cleared out” and connected with a future away from the substances. The final step in this process is the acceptance of the grief caused by the distancing from the substances, a fact, which presupposes the activation of certain psychic mechanisms. Characteristic of this procedure is that these two steps are many times intermixed, a fact, which shows the serious emotional blocking of the user. The proper formation of a therapeutic request also operates as a precaution towards the prevention of a future relapse (Matsa K. 1998¹⁹).

Concerning the theory of nine (9) points, we can conclusively mention the following: There are facts before the use (Points 1 and 2), which can be very important for the future course of the user. They are also important for the formation of a personal therapeutic request. It seems that the emotional imbalance and inactivity during these time periods lead to serious and increasing difficulties of communication. This communication difficulty is a condition, which can lead to the use of psychotropic substances. The attractiveness and desire to become acquainted with what is forbidden (i.e. the substances) (Point 3), as well as the gradual need for “toxic” pleasure and euphoria (Point 4), are also important elements.

It is true that the user, after the establishment of the use, develops a kind of “toxic emotion”, which gradually penetrates his/her whole existence and “toxically” saturates all his/her experiences. During the completion of this process, we can observe the establishment of the vicious circle of dependence (Points 5, 6 and 7). The final recess (Point 8) and the phase of exit from the use (Point 9), can be only realized if the user accepts that the conditions of his/her life are problematic and understands himself/herself in depth.

The theory of nine (9) points shows how important is our understanding of the emotional life of the users, because this is the only way we can really intervene therapeutically, and the only way they can understand.

Undoubtedly, the parental environment has a major influence during the formation of the first two periods before the use (Points 1 and 2), and certainly the parents have the responsibility and choice for the formation of the codes of communication within the family, which lead to particular emotional expressions by the rest of the members (Matsa K. 2000²¹; Moros N. 1988²⁸). If this communication is characterized as problematic, concerning its expression, it will certainly lead to impassable situations later. For this reason, the specialist, who will apply the technique of the procedure for the formation of a personal therapeutic request for the user, must also be aware of these facts from the parents’ point of view. It is indeed obvious that if we later realize that there is a defective and “weak” communication towards one or more members of a family, which faces the problem of the use, this will come too late. The rest of the broader environment is called to be placed within these conditions and support psychologically and ethically the members of this family. The pressure put upon them is sometimes unbearable and irrational. For this reason, they also need guidance because they are “in danger” of becoming the “scapegoats” of the situation.

The theory of nine (9) points can become a useful tool in the hands of the specialists, which can lead to a safe formation of a personal therapeutic request for the users of psychotropic substances. It is important that we can develop this theory and formulate the necessary therapeutic tools, which will lead to the evaluation of the emotional intelligence of the users. I believe that the best knowledge of Points 1 and 2 will assist in the better formation of the programmes of prevention.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

QUESTIONNAIRE

Research and Background of the Use of Psychotropic Substances

1. At what age did you start using illegal psychotropic substances? _____
2. Are you a tobacco user (nicotine)?
 YES NO
 If YES, since what age? _____
3. Are you an alcohol user?
 YES NO
 If YES, since what age? _____
4. Do you use other psychotropic legal substances [benzine, glue]?
 YES NO
 If YES, since what age? _____
5. Which are the illegal psychotropic substances you used during the last 6 months?
Tick the kind of substance and underline the form wherever it is mentioned
 - Hemp [hashish, paste]
 - Heroin [cotton, sniff, smoked, needle]
 - Cocaine [powder, freebase]
 - Pills [stedon, hypnostedon, vulbegal]
 - Ecstasy [noname, mdma]
 - LSD
 - Amphetamines
 - Anabolic substances
 - Other _____

6. Which, do you think, is/are the illegal substance/s you mostly needed during the last 2 months?

Tick the kind, underline the form wherever it is mentioned and write down the quantity

Product	Quantity/Week
<input type="checkbox"/> Hemp [hashish, paste]	No. of Cigarettes:
<input type="checkbox"/> Heroin [cotton, sniff, smoked, needle]	No. of Doses:
<input type="checkbox"/> Cocaine [powder, freebase]	No. of Doses:
<input type="checkbox"/> Pills [stedon, hypnosodon, vulbegal]	No. of Pills:
<input type="checkbox"/> Ecstasy [noname, mdma]	No. of Pills:
<input type="checkbox"/> LSD	No. of Pills:
<input type="checkbox"/> Aphetamines	No. of Pills:
<input type="checkbox"/> Anabolic substances	No. of Pills:
Other:	No. :

7. Would you rather have more quantity of the substances you use than the one you mentioned at the above table?

YES NO

8. Who introduced you to the use of illegal --- substances?

Friends

My partner

Relatives

Family environment

By my self

Other: _____

9. You allowed yourself to taste the substances for reasons of:

Curiosity

Boredom

Fashion

Being street wise

Stupidity

Bad psychological mood

Good psychological mood

No particular reason

Other: _____

10. For what reasons, do you believe, you continued using illegal psycotropic substances?

I liked being stoned

I liked illegality

I felt powerful-strong

I did not feel bad any more

It was too late to escape

Other: _____

11. Within the last 2 moths, do you have a permanent job?

YES NO

If YES, how long do you have this job? _____

12. Are you satisfied from you job?

YES NO

13. Did you have a permanent residence during the last 2 months?

YES NO

If YES:

You live by your self

You live with your partner

You live with others

You live with your family

You live in a friend's house

You live in relatives' house

Other: _____

If NO, why? _____

14. Did you have a stable relationship/love affair during the last 6 months?

YES NO

15. During the last 2 months, did have friends who are "clean"?

YES NO

16. Does your family know you are a user of illegal psychotropic substances?

YES NO

17. How would you characterize your relationship with your family during the last 3 months?

Evaluate with grading from 1 to 7, where 1=hostile, 7=very good.

18. Describe any medical problems or illnesses that appeared after the beginning of your use of substances?

19. Did any of the above problems involve treatment in a hospital?

YES NO

If YES, for how long _____ and for what problem

20. Have you been treated in a psychiatric hospital?

YES NO

If YES, was it because of substance use?

YES NO

If NO, describe the reason

For _____ how _____ long?

Do you know what was the psychiatric diagnosis?

21. Have you been under legal medication, during the last month?

YES NO

If YES, for what reason _____

and _____ what _____ kind _____ of _____ medication

22. Have you ever been presented in a Police Station for personal records verification?

YES NO

23. Do you have any pending judicial affairs?

YES NO

If YES, what for?

24. Are there any final verdicts, which concern you?

YES NO

If YES, for what offences?

25. Have you ever been imprisoned?

YES NO

If YES, was it because of substance use?

YES NO

If you have been imprisoned but not because of substance use, describe the reason

26. Have you ever attempted to cut off the substance use before?

YES NO

27. Have you attempted to cut off the substance use during the last 6 months?

YES NO

If YES, in what way?

By myself at home

By myself, outside the house

With the help of a specialist

Through a dryly therapeutic programme

Through a therapeutic programme which involved substitutes

Other: _____

28. Which do you think were the reasons you didn't make it until now?

- I wasn't really ready
- I didn't do it for me
- I am afraid of the private symptoms
- I get carried away easily

Other: _____

29. Do you wish to stop using substances?

- YES NO

If YES, why do you believe you will make it this time?

30. What do you think is required so that you can stop the use?

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